

A Study to assess the Web Series Addiction and Sleeping Pattern among College Students Studying in Selected Colleges at Aluva

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken to evaluate the relationship between sleeping pattern and web series addiction among college students in selected colleges at Aluva. The study aimed to assess the level of web series addiction among college students, to assess the sleeping pattern of college students, to assess the relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among the college students studying in the various colleges of Aluva, to find the association between web series addiction and selected demographic variables of college students, and to find the association between sleeping pattern and selected demographic variables of college students. The research design that the researcher used in the study was quantitative descriptive correlational research design. The study was conducted among college students of Union Christian College, Aluva. Simple random sampling technique was used to select a total of 60 samples who met the inclusion criteria. The data collection tool consisted of demographic variables, sleeping pattern questionnaire, and web series addiction questionnaire. The data were collected by using direct questionnaire method for easy collection of data. The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were maintained throughout the study. The data were collected after obtaining permission from the

concerned authorities and informed consent from the participants.

The data collected were organized, tabulated and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that most of the college students had poor sleeping pattern and moderate level of web series addiction. There was a significant relationship between sleeping pattern and web series addiction among college students. There was significant association between web series addiction and selected demographic variables such as year or semester of study and hours of watching web series. The study found that excessive web series addiction had a significant impact on sleeping pattern among college students. Early identification and management of web series addiction may help in promoting healthy sleeping pattern and overall well-being among college students.

Chapter 1 Introduction

Background of the Study

The rapid advancement of digital technology and the widespread availability of high-speed internet services have significantly transformed the lifestyle and entertainment habits of young adults. In recent years, online streaming platforms have become one of the most common sources of

recreation, replacing traditional television viewing among many individuals. These platforms provide instant access to movies, television programs, and web series at any time and place through smartphones, tablets, laptops, and smart televisions. Among these forms of entertainment, web series have become especially popular among college students because of their engaging storylines, relatable characters, short episodic format, and the convenience of watching according to personal schedules. The features of automatic next-episode play, personalized recommendations, and availability of complete seasons often encourage prolonged viewing sessions, commonly known as binge-watching. While moderate viewing may offer enjoyment, relaxation, and temporary stress relief, excessive and uncontrolled viewing can gradually lead to addictive behaviours¹

Web series addiction refers to a pattern of compulsive watching in which an individual feels a strong urge to continue viewing despite negative consequences. Such individuals may lose track of time, neglect academic tasks, postpone daily responsibilities, reduce social interaction, and experience difficulty stopping after one or two episodes. This behavioural pattern resembles other forms of digital addiction where entertainment consumption becomes difficult to control. The increasing affordability of smartphones and internet data packages has made continuous streaming more accessible than ever before, thereby increasing the risk of problematic viewing habits among youth.

College students are particularly vulnerable to developing web series addiction because they are in a stage of transition marked by greater independence, changing social roles, and exposure to new academic and emotional challenges. Many students live away from home for the first time and experience reduced parental supervision, allowing them to manage their own schedules without strict control. Academic workload, examination stress, peer pressure, loneliness, relationship issues, and uncertainty about the future may contribute to emotional distress. In such situations, web series may become an easily available coping mechanism to escape stress, boredom, or anxiety. What begins as a leisure activity may gradually become a repetitive habit that interferes with healthy daily routines.

Sleep is one of the most essential biological functions required for growth, restoration, learning, and psychological well-being. Adequate sleep is necessary for maintaining concentration, memory, decision-making ability, emotional regulation, and physical health. Young adults generally need sufficient nightly sleep to function effectively in educational and social settings. However, sleep problems are increasingly common among college students due to irregular schedules, academic deadlines, social commitments, and excessive screen use. Watching web series late into the night often delays bedtime and reduces total sleep duration. Furthermore, exposure to blue light emitted from digital screens may suppress melatonin secretion, delay sleep onset, and disturb the body's natural circadian rhythm^{2,3}

Poor sleeping patterns among college students may include late sleeping hours, difficulty falling asleep, interrupted sleep, reduced sleep duration, excessive daytime sleepiness, and inconsistent wake-up times. Such disturbances may result in fatigue, headaches, poor concentration, irritability, mood swings, reduced motivation, and impaired academic performance. Students suffering from inadequate sleep may find it difficult to attend early morning classes, participate actively in learning activities, or maintain healthy relationships. Long-term sleep deprivation can also contribute to anxiety, depression, obesity, lowered immunity, and other health concerns.

The relationship between web series addiction and sleeping patterns is becoming an important public health concern. Students who binge-watch episodes often intend to watch for a short period but continue for several hours due to suspenseful endings, emotional attachment to characters, and curiosity about future episodes. Streaming platforms are specifically designed to maximize user engagement through autoplay features and tailored suggestions, making it easier for viewers to continue watching unconsciously. As a result, bedtime is delayed repeatedly, creating a cycle of sleep debt and daytime tiredness. Many students may compensate by napping during the day, consuming caffeine, or skipping academic tasks, which may further disturb normal sleep routines.

In addition to affecting sleep, excessive web series consumption may also influence

psychological and social well-being. Students may experience guilt after wasting time, anxiety about unfinished work, reduced face-to-face interaction, and increased social isolation. Some may prioritize watching web series over exercise, hobbies, or spending time with family and friends. This imbalance in lifestyle behaviours can reduce overall quality of life and negatively affect personal development during an important stage of adulthood.

Although many studies have explored the impact of social media addiction, smartphone dependence, and general screen time on sleep quality, comparatively fewer studies have specifically focused on web series addiction and its relationship with sleeping patterns among college students. Web series consumption may differ from other digital activities because of its narrative continuity, emotional engagement, and binge-watching tendency. Therefore, it is important to study this phenomenon separately to understand its specific effects on student health and behaviour

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The college period is a crucial stage for establishing lifelong habits related to health, time management, and emotional coping. Unhealthy patterns developed during these years may continue into later adulthood and affect future productivity and well-being. Identifying modifiable factors such as excessive web series viewing can help educational institutions and healthcare professionals design preventive measures, counseling strategies, and awareness programs. Promoting responsible digital media use and good sleep hygiene practices may significantly improve student health outcomes.

Therefore, the present study aims to assess the level of web series addiction and examine its relationship with sleeping patterns among college students. The findings of this study may provide valuable insights for educators, parents, mental health professionals, and policymakers in developing suitable interventions to promote healthy entertainment habits, balanced use of digital technology, and better sleep practices among students.

Need of the Study

This study aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on web series addiction and its impact on sleeping patterns among college students. With the rapid increase in OTT

platform usage, excessive binge-watching has become a common habit, especially among adolescents and young adults. This study provides insights into the causes, consequences, and possible interventions.

* Growing prevalence

The popularity of OTT platforms like Netflix, Amazon Prime, and Hotstar has led to increased binge-watching among students, raising concerns about addiction.

* Sleep disturbances

Excessive watching of web series, especially at night, disrupts sleep cycles, leading to insomnia, poor sleep quality, and daytime fatigue.

* Mental health concerns

Web series addiction is associated with stress, anxiety, depression, and reduced emotional well-being.

* Impact on academic performance

Lack of proper sleep and excessive screen time negatively affect concentration, memory, and academic performance.

* Impact on physical health

Sedentary behaviour, eye strain, and fatigue are common consequences of prolonged screen exposure.

* Understanding behavioural patterns

The study helps identify psychological and social factors contributing to addiction, such as peer influence and escapism.

* Guiding interventions

Findings can help educators and healthcare professionals develop strategies to promote healthy media consumption.

* Raising awareness

This study creates awareness among students about the risks of binge-watching and the importance of sleep hygiene.

Problem Statement

A study to assess the web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in selected colleges at Aluva

Objectives

- To assess the level of web series addiction among college students.
- To assess the sleeping pattern of college students.
- To assess the relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in various colleges of Aluva

- To find the association between web series addiction and selected demographical variables of college students.
- To find the association between sleeping pattern and selected demographical variables of college students.

Purposes

- To define and measure web series addiction.
- To evaluate sleep patterns among college students.
- To identify the relationship between binge-watching and sleep disturbances.
- To study the negative consequences such as poor academic performance, stress, and fatigue.

Operational Definitions

Web Series:

A web series refers to episodic video content available on online streaming platforms, often watched continuously (binge-watching).

Web Series Addiction:

A behavioural pattern characterized by excessive and compulsive watching of web series, leading to neglect of daily activities, poor sleep, and negative physical or mental effects.

Sleeping Pattern:

Refers to the duration, quality, and regularity of sleep, including sleep time, wake time, and disturbances.

College Students:

Individuals enrolled in undergraduate or postgraduate programs in selected colleges at Aluva.

Level:

Refers to the degree or extent of web series addiction or sleep disturbance measured using a structured scale.

Hypothesis

H0-There is no significant relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students.

H1-There is a significant relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students.

H2-There is a significant association between web series addiction and selected demographic variables.

Limitations

- The study is limited to selected colleges at Aluva, so findings may not be generalized to all college students.
- The sample size may be small, which can affect the accuracy of results.

Delimitation

- The study is restricted to college students in selected colleges at Aluva.
- Only students who are willing to participate are included.

Summary

This chapter dealt with background, need of the study, problem statement, objectives, operational definition, hypothesis, limitations and delimitation.

Chapter 2 Review of Literature

Review of Literature

“Review of literature is an important step in the development of a research project it involves systematic identification of location, scrutiny and survey of written material that contain information on research problem”

Review of literature are under the following headings

I. Studies Related to Web Series Addiction of college students.

- The Study was conducted in India to assess binge-watching behaviour among college students. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. The sample size was 200 college students, selected using convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a self-structured binge-watching questionnaire.

The results of the study revealed that a majority of college students engaged in prolonged web series watching, experienced loss of control over viewing time, and showed signs of craving and compulsive behaviour, indicating moderate levels of web series addiction.⁵

- The study was conducted in the United States among university students to explore binge-watching habits.

- The study employed a descriptive research design. The sample consisted of 150 students, selected through purposive sampling technique. Data were collected using a binge-watching engagement scale. The findings showed that easy accessibility of streaming platforms and auto-play features encouraged continuous watching, leading to addictive viewing patterns and reduced self-control among students⁶.
- The study was conducted in Belgium to assess binge-watching engagement and symptoms among young adults. The study used a quantitative research design. The sample size was 312, selected using random sampling technique. Data were collected using the Binge-Watching Engagement and Symptoms Questionnaire (BWESQ). The study results indicated that higher engagement scores were associated with emotional dependence, escapism, and compulsive watching behaviour, suggesting problematic binge-watching tendencies.
- The study was conducted in Poland among university students to assess problematic binge-watching behaviour. The study followed a cross-sectional design. The sample size was 420, selected using convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a standardized binge-watching addiction scale. The findings revealed that a significant number of students had moderate to severe levels of binge-watching addiction, which negatively affected their academic activities and daily routines⁸.
- The study was conducted in India to assess web series addiction among college students. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The sample consisted of 180 students, selected using convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a self-structured questionnaire. The results showed that more than half of the students had moderate levels of web series addiction, with increased screen time and neglect of academic and social activities⁹.

II. Studies Related to Sleeping Pattern among College Students.

- The study was conducted in the United States to assess sleep habits among college students. The study used a descriptive research design. The sample size was 300, selected through random sampling technique. Data were collected using a sleep habits questionnaire.

The study findings revealed that irregular sleep schedules, late bedtime, and insufficient sleep duration were common among college students and adversely affected their academic performance and daytime functioning¹⁰.

- The study was conducted in Switzerland to examine the effect of screen exposure on sleep quality among young adults. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. The sample size was 362, selected using systematic sampling technique. Data were collected using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI). The results indicated that increased screen exposure before bedtime significantly delayed sleep onset and reduced overall sleep quality¹¹.
- The study was conducted in India to assess sleeping patterns among medical and nursing students. The study followed a descriptive research design. The sample consisted of 200 students, selected using convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a sleep pattern questionnaire. The findings showed that a majority of students experienced poor sleep quality, frequent night-time awakenings, and excessive daytime sleepiness¹².
- The study was conducted in South India to assess sleep duration and quality among college students. The study employed a cross-sectional design. The sample size was 250, selected using random sampling technique. Data were collected using the PSQI tool. The results revealed that more than 60% of students had disturbed sleeping patterns and inadequate sleep duration¹³.
- The study was conducted in Tamil Nadu, India among arts and science college students. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The sample size was 180, selected through convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a self-structured sleep questionnaire. The study concluded that irregular bedtimes and excessive screen usage contributed significantly to poor sleep quality among students¹⁴.

III. Studies Related to the Relationship between Web Series Addiction and Sleeping Pattern

- The study was conducted in Belgium to examine the relationship between binge-watching and sleep quality among young adults. The study used a correlational research design. The sample size was 423, selected using random sampling technique. Data were collected using a binge-watching scale and PSQI.

The results showed a significant relationship between binge-watching behaviour and delayed bedtime, reduced sleep duration, and increased fatigue¹⁵.

- The study was conducted in South Korea among university students to assess the relationship between binge-watching and sleep patterns. The study adopted a cross-sectional design. The sample consisted of 240 students, selected using convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a binge-watching questionnaire and sleep quality scale.

The findings revealed that excessive binge-watching was associated with poor sleep quality, difficulty initiating sleep, and daytime sleepiness¹⁶.

- The study was conducted in the United States to examine the relationship between screen exposure and sleep patterns. The study followed a descriptive correlational design. The sample size was 200, selected using random sampling technique. Data were collected using

a screen-time assessment tool and sleep questionnaire.

The study results showed that prolonged screen exposure before bedtime disrupted circadian rhythm and sleep-wake cycles¹⁷.

- The study was conducted in India among college students to assess the relationship between binge-watching and sleep quality. The study used a cross-sectional research design. The sample size was 300, selected using convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a binge-watching scale and PSQI. The findings revealed a significant negative relationship between binge-watching behaviour and sleep quality, with students reporting insomnia and fatigue¹⁸.

- The study was conducted in Kerala, India to assess the relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students. The study adopted a correlational research design. The sample consisted of 180 students, selected using convenience sampling technique. Data were collected using a web series addiction scale and sleep pattern questionnaire.

The results showed that higher levels of web series addiction were significantly associated with disturbed sleeping patterns and increased daytime sleepiness¹⁹.

Chapter 3

Methodology

The techniques used to structure a study to gather and analyse information in a systematic fashion.

— Polit and Beck

This chapter deals with the research approach, research design, setting of the study, population, sample and sampling technique, inclusion criteria, data collection instruments, data collection process and plan for data analysis.

Research Approach

Research approach is the basic procedure for conducting a research inquiry and determines what data to collect and how to analyse it.

In view of the nature of the problem and to accomplish the objectives of the study, a quantitative approach was considered appropriate to assess the relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students in selected colleges at Aluva.

Assumptions

In the present study, it is assumed that:

- Sleep is a basic human need essential for maintaining physical and mental health.
- Web series watching is a common activity among college students.
- Excessive watching of web series may affect normal sleeping patterns.
- Sleep pattern can be influenced by behavioral and lifestyle factors.

Hypotheses

H₀ - There is no significant relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in selected colleges at Aluva.

H₁ - There is a significant relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in selected colleges at Aluva.

H₂ - There is a significant association between web series addiction and selected demographic variables (such as age, gender, course, duration of watching, etc.) among college students.

Variables

Variables are the characteristics or attributes that can be measured in research. Independent variable: Web series addiction

Socio-Personal Variables

Socio-personal variables included in the study are: Age (in years)
Gender Religion
Course/Department Type of residence
Occupation of father Occupation of mother
Duration of web series watching
Availability of internet/device

Attribute Variables

In the present study, attribute variables are used to assess the addiction and sleeping pattern among college students under selected demographic variables.

Setting

The study was conducted in Union Christian College, Aluva.

Population

The population of the study consists of college students studying in selected colleges at Aluva.

Sample and Sample Size

The study was conducted among 60 students from UC College, Aluva

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used for the present study is purposive sampling.

Sampling Criteria**Inclusion Criteria**

College students aged between 18–25 years studying in selected colleges at Aluva Students who are available at the time of data collection
Students who are willing to participate

Exclusion Criteria

Students diagnosed with sleep disorders

Data Collection Tools

Data collection tools refer to the devices used to gather information relevant to the study. In this study, the tools used were demographic preform, web series addiction scale and sleeping pattern scale.

Dependent variable: Sleeping pattern

Demographic variables: Age, gender, course, residence, etc.

Tool 1: Demographic Proforma of College Students

It consists of demographic variables such as age, gender, religion, course, type of residence, occupation of parents, duration of watching web series and availability of internet/device.

Tool 2: Rating Scale to Assess Web Series Addiction

A structured rating scale was used to assess the level of web series addiction. It consists of 20 items

Each item has 4 responses:

Strongly agree – 4 Agree – 3
Disagree – 2

Strongly Disagree– 1

Scoring Interpretation:

0–19: No addiction

20–39: Mild addiction

40–59: Moderate addiction

60–80: Severe addiction

Tool 3: Rating Scale To Assess Sleeping Pattern

A structured questionnaire was used to assess sleeping patterns. Includes questions on duration, quality, disturbances and sleep habits
Response Options for ALL Questions:

Never - 1
Rarely – 2
Sometimes - 3
Frequently - 4
Always - 5

Interpretation

10-21 - Good sleep hygiene

22-31 - Moderate sleep hygiene

32-50- Poor sleep hygiene

Data Collection

Data was collected using structured questionnaires on web series addiction and sleeping pattern, along with demographic Performa.

Data Analysis

Data analysis is the process of systematically applying statistical techniques to describe and evaluate data.

Descriptive statistics: Frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation

Inferential statistics: Correlation and chi-square test to find association between variables

Summary

This chapter dealt with research approach, research design, setting, population, sample, sampling technique, tools for data collection, and plan for data analysis. The study used a quantitative approach with descriptive correlational design to assess the relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students.

Chapter 4**Analysis and Interpretation****Analysis and Interpretation of Data**

The analysis refers to the computation of collected data and identification of relationships among variables. This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the study conducted to assess the level of web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students. The data were analysed and interpreted based on the objectives and hypotheses of the study.

Problem Statement

A study to assess the level of web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in selected colleges at Aluva.

Objectives

- To assess the level of web series addiction among college students.
- To assess the sleeping pattern of college students.
- To assess the relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in various colleges of Aluva.

- To find the association between web series addiction and selected demographical variables of college students.
- To find the association between sleeping pattern and selected demographical variables of college students.

Hypothesis

All the hypothesis will be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀ -There is no significant association between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students.

H₁ - There is a significant association between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students.

Analysis and Interpretation Section 1: Demographic Data

Table: 1.1 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on age (n= 60)

SL. NO	Age Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	17 – 19 Years	15	25%
2	20 - 22 Years	11	18%
3	23 – 25 Years	26	44%
4.	23 and Above	8	13%

Fig1.1 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on age

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to age category 23-25 (44%) Followed by category 17-19 (25%).

categories (20-22years) and (23 and above) represent smaller portions of the sample.

Table 1.2 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Gender (n=60)

SL.NO	Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Male	23	38.4%
2	Female	37	61.6%
3	Transgender	0	0

Fig 1.2 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Gender.

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to gender category female (61.6%). Followed by category male (38.4%).

Table 1.3 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Course of study. (n=60)

SL.NO	Course of study	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Arts and Humanities	60	100%
2	Science and Technology	0	0
3	Health Sciences	0	0
3	Legal studies	0	0

Fig 1.3 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Course of study.

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to course of study category Arts and Humanities (100%).

Table 1 .4 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Year/Semester. (n=60)

SL.NO	Year/Semester	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	First Year	33	55%
2	Second Year	7	12%
3	Third Year	14	23%
4	Post graduate	6	10%

Figure 1 .4 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Year/Semester.

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to year/semester category first year (55%) Followed by category third year (23%). categories second year and post graduate represent smaller portions of the sample.

Table 1 .5 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on place of living (n=60)

SL.NO	Place of living	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Hostel	19	32%
2	Own Home	37	61%
3	Paying Guest	4	7%
4	Rental	0	0

Fig 1 .5 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on place of living.

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to place of living category own home (61%). Followed by category hostel (32%). categories paying guest and rental represent smaller portions of the sample.

Table 1.6 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on device mainly used to watch web series. (n=60)

SL.NO	Device Usage	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Mobile	43	72%
2	Laptop	7	12%
3	Smart TV	8	13%
4	Tablet	2	3%

Fig 1.6 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on device mainly used to watch web series.

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to device mainly used to watch web series category mobile (72%). Followed by

category smart TV (13%). categories laptop and tablet represent smaller portions of the sample.

Table 1 .7 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Average

hours spent watching web series per day. (n=60)

SL.NO	Average hours	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Less than 1 hour	8	13%
2	1 - 2hours	12	20%
3	2 – 4 hours	24	40%
4	More than 4 hour	16	27%

Fig 1 .7 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Average hours spent watching web series per day.

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to average hours spend while watching web series per day category 2-4 hours (40%). Followed by category more than 4 hours (27%). categories <1 hour and 1-2 hour

represent smaller portions of the sample. **Table 1.8** Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Hobbies. (n=60)

SL.NO	Hobbies	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Watching Reels	12	20%
2	Watching web series	24	40%
3	Watching film	12	20%
4	Other	12	20%

Fig 1.8 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on Hobbies.

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to hobbies category watching web series (40%). Followed by category Watching Reels, Watching film and other (20%).

Table 1.9 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on locality (n=60)

SL.NO	Locality	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Urban	14	23%
2	Semi urban	28	47%
3	Rural	15	25%
4	Semi-rural	3	5%

Fig 1 .9 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on locality

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to locality category semi urban (47%). Followed by category rural (25%). categories urban and semi-rural represent smaller portions of the sample.

Table 1 .10 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on socio economic status (n=60)

SL.NO	Socio economic status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Upper	3	5%
2	Upper middle	22	37%
3	Middle	35	58%
4	Lower	0	0

Fig 1 .10 Frequency and percentage of distribution of samples based on socio economic status

Interpretation: Majority of participants belong to socio-economic status category middle (58%). Followed by category upper

middle (37%). categories upper and lower represent smaller portions of the sample.

Section 2: Description of Level of Web Series Addiction

TABLE 2.1: Frequency and percentage distribution of samples according to level of

web series addiction.

SL NO	WEB SERIES ADDICTION	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
1	MILD ADDICTION	9	16%
2	MODERATE ADDICTION	36	62%
3	SEVERE ADDICTION	13	22%

A descriptive analysis was conducted on web series addiction scores are collected from 60 participants. The web series addiction score was assessed by web series addiction scale. To understand the severity levels of web series

addiction among participants the scores were categorized into: Most of the respondents experienced moderate levels of web series addiction.

- Mild Addiction -9 participants (16%)
- Moderate Addiction -36 participants (62%)
- Severe Addiction- 13 participants (22%)

Figure 2.2: Pie diagram showing level of web series addiction.

The figure 2.2 shows that out of 60 samples they are scored as mild, moderate and severe. And about, 16% of subject has mild level of web series addiction, 62% of subject has moderate level of web series addiction and 22% have severe level of addiction.

Section 3: Description of Level Of Sleeping Pattern

TABLE 3.1: Frequency and percentage distribution of samples according to level of sleeping pattern of students

SL NO	Sleeping Pattern	Frequency	Percentage %
1	Good Sleep Hygiene	6	10%
2.	Moderate Sleep Hygiene	29	48.4%
3.	Poor Sleep Hygiene	25	41.6%

To understand the severity levels of sleeping pattern among participants the scores were categorized into:

- Good Sleeping Hygien – 6 participants (10%)
- Moderate Sleeping Hygiene – 29 participants (48.4%)
- Poor Sleeping Hygiene – 25 participants (41.6%)

Most of the respondents experienced moderate levels of sleeping pattern

The figure 3.2: Bar diagram showing level of sleeping pattern

The figure 3.2 shows that out of 60 samples they are scored as good, moderate and severe. And about, 10% of subject has good level of sleeping pattern, 48.4% of subject has moderate level of sleeping pattern and 41.6% of subject has poor sleep hygiene

Summary

This chapter dealt with analysis and interpretation of data. The study assessed web series addiction and sleeping patterns among 60 college students and found that the majority (62%) had moderate levels of web series

addiction, while 22% showed severe addiction and 16% had mild addiction, indicating a high prevalence of media overuse. In terms of sleeping patterns, 48.4% of students had moderate sleep hygiene and 41.6% had poor sleep hygiene, with only 10% maintaining good sleep habits. Overall, the findings suggest that most students experience both moderate addiction to web series and inadequate sleep patterns, highlighting a possible negative relationship between excessive web series consumption and poor sleep hygiene among college students.

Section 4: Relationship Between Web Series

Addiction And Sleeping Pattern

Table: 4.1 Correlation Matrix

		WBT	SLT
WBT	Pearson's r	—	
	df	—	
	p-value	—	
SLT	Pearson's r	0.276	—
	df	58	—
	p-value	.033	—

Interpretation: “The analysis showed a significant association between WBT and SLT, $r(58) = 0.276$, $p = 0.033$. The correlation indicates a weak positive relationship between web series addiction and sleep disturbances, suggesting that

higher levels of WBT are associated with increased SLT levels.”

Section 5 : Association Between Web Series Addiction And Selected Demographic Variables

Table: 5.1 Contingency Tables-

	SD1				
WBI	1	2	3	4	Total
Mild	3	2	2	0	7
Moderate	10	7	18	5	40
Severe	2	2	6	3	13
Total	15	11	26	8	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	d f	p
χ^2	4.13	6	.659
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between WBI level and SD1 (age) category, $\chi^2 (6, N = 60) = 4.13, p = 0.659$. The distribution of SD1 categories did not

differ across WBI levels, with similar patterns of mild, moderate, and severe categories observed across all groups.”

Table: 5.2 Contingency Tables

	SD2		
WBI	1	2	Total
Mild	4	3	7
Moderate	14	26	40
Severe	5	8	13
Total	23	37	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	1.24	2	.539
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between WBI level and SD2 (gender) category, $\chi^2 (2, N = 60) = 1.24, p = 0.539$. The distribution of SD2 categories did not differ across WBI levels, with similar patterns of

mild, moderate, and severe categories observed across the groups.”

Table: 5.3 Contingency Tables

SI No	Web Series Addiction	Frequency	Percentage %
1	Mild Addiction	9	16%
2	Moderate Addiction	36	62%
3	Severe Addiction	13	22%

Interpretation: The findings reveal that the majority of college students had moderate level of web series addiction (62%), followed by severe addiction (22%), while only 16% of

students had mild addiction. This indicates that most students are moderately addicted to web series, with a considerable proportion also experiencing severe addiction.

Table: 5.4 Contingency Tables

	SD4				
WBI	1	2	3	4	Total
Mild	6	0	0	1	7
Moderate	23	2	13	2	40
Severe	4	3	3	3	13
Total	33	5	16	6	60

X ² Tests			
	Value	Df	P
X ²	12.9	6	.044
N	60		

Interpretation: “The Analysis Showed a Significant Association between WBI Level Categories Differed Across WBI Levels, With Variations Observed In The Proportions Of Mild, Moderate, And Severe Categories Across

and SD4 (year/semester) Category, X² (6, N = 60) = 12.9, P = 0.044. The Distribution Of SD4 The Groups.”

Table: 5.5 Contingency Tables

	SD5			
WBI	1	2	3	Total
Mild	3	3	1	7
Moderate	11	26	3	40
Severe	5	8	0	13
Total	19	37	4	60

χ ² Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ ²	2.68	4	.613
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between WBI level and SD5 (place of living) category, χ²(4, N = 60) = 2.68, p = 0.613. The distribution of SD5

categories did not differ significantly across WBI levels, with similar proportions of mild, moderate, and severe categories observed across the groups.”

Table: 5.6 Contingency Tables

	SD6				
WBI	1	2	3	4	Total
Mild	6	0	1	0	7
Moderate	30	3	5	2	40
Severe	7	5	1	0	13
Total	43	8	7	2	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	10.2	6	.117
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between WBI level and SD6 (devices) category, χ^2 (6, N = 60) = 10.2, p = 0.117. The distribution of SD6 categories did not differ significantly across WBI levels, with variations **D4yuy**

observed in the proportions of mild, moderate, and severe categories across the groups.”

Table: 5.7 Contingency Tables

	SD7				
WBI	1	2	3	4	Total
Mild	4	2	1	0	7
Moderate	5	8	15	12	40
Severe	0	2	8	3	13
Total	9	12	24	15	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	15.7	6	.015
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed a significant association between WBI level and SD7 (hours) category, $\chi^2(6, N = 60) = 15.7, p = 0.015$. The distribution of SD7 categories differed across WBI levels, with varying

patterns observed among mild, moderate, and severe groups.”

Table: 5.8 Contingency Tables

	SD8				
WBI	1	2	3	4	Total
mild	0	3	2	2	7
moderate	9	14	8	9	40
severe	2	7	3	1	13
Total	11	24	13	12	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	4.20	6	.650
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between WBI level and SD9 category (hobbies), $\chi^2 (6, N = 60) = 12.0, p = 0.062$. The distribution of SD9 categories did not differ across WBI levels, with similar

patterns observed among mild, moderate, and severe groups.”

Table: 5.9 Contingency Tables

	SD9				
WBI	1	2	3	4	Total
mild	0	2	4	1	7
moderate	9	23	7	1	40
severe	5	4	4	0	13
Total	14	29	15	2	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	12.0	6	.062
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between WBI level and SD9 category (locality), χ^2 (6, N = 60) = 12.0, p = 0.062. The distribution of SD9 categories did not differ across WBI levels,

with similar patterns observed among mild, moderate, and severe groups.”

Table: 5.10 Contingency Tables

	SD10			
WBI	1	2	3	Total
Mild	0	2	5	7
Moderate	3	3	34	40
Severe	0	3	10	13
Total	3	8	49	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	4.85	4	.304
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between WBI level and SD10 (socio-economic status) category, χ^2 (4, N = 60) = 4.85, p = 0.304. The distribution of SD10 categories did not differ across WBI

levels, with similar patterns observed among mild, moderate, and severe groups.”

Section 6: Association Between Sleeping Pattern And Selected Demographic Variables

Table: 6.1 Contingency Tables

	SD1				
SLI	1	2	3	4	Total
Good	2	2	0	2	6
Moderate	8	6	14	1	29
Poor	5	3	12	5	25
Total	15	11	26	8	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	9.51	6	.147
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD1 (age) category, $\chi^2 (6, N = 60) = 9.51, p = 0.147$. The distribution of SD1 categories did not differ across SLI levels, with similar

patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.”

Table:6.2ContingencyTable

	SD2		
SLI	1	2	Total
Good	3	3	6
Moderate	12	17	29
Poor	8	17	25
Total	23	37	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	0.884	2	.643
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD2 (gender) category, $\chi^2 (2, N = 60) = 0.884, p = 0.643$. The distribution of SD2 categories

did not differ across SLI levels, with similar patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups”

Table: 6.3 Contingency Tables

Sl No	Sleeping Pattern	Frequency	Percentage %
1	Good Sleep Hygiene	6	10%
2.	Moderate Sleep Hygiene	29	48.4%
3.	Poor Sleep Hygiene	25	41.6%

Interpretation: he findings show that nearly half of the students had moderate sleep hygiene (48.4%), followed by poor sleep hygiene (41.6%), while only 10% of students had good sleep hygiene. This indicates that most students have

unsatisfactory sleeping patterns, with a considerable proportion experiencing poor sleep hygiene.

Table:6.4 Contingency Tables

SLI	SD4				Total
	1	2	3	4	
Good	5	0	1	0	6
Moderate	18	1	6	4	29
Poor	10	4	9	2	25
Total	33	5	16	6	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	7.80	6	.253
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD4 (year/semester) category, χ^2 (6, N = 60) = 7.80, p = 0.253. The distribution of SD4 categories did not differ across SLI levels, with similar patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.”

Table: 6.5 Contingency Tables

	SD5			
SLI	1	2	3	Total
Good	2	4	0	6
Moderate	5	21	3	29
Poor	12	12	1	25
Total	19	37	4	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	d f	p
χ^2	6.60	4	.159
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD5 (place of living) category, χ^2 (4, N = 60) = 6.60, p = 0.159. The distribution of SD5

categories did not differ across SLI levels, with similar patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.”

Table: 6.6 Contingency Tables

	SD6				
SLI	1	2	3	4	Total
Good	3	0	2	1	6
Moderate	21	4	3	1	29
Poor	19	4	2	0	25
Total	43	8	7	2	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	d f	p
χ^2	8.18	6	.225
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD6 (devices) category, $\chi^2 (6, N = 60) = 8.18$, $p = 0.225$. The distribution of SD6 categories did not differ across SLI levels, with similar

patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.”

Table: 6.7 Contingency Tables

	SD7				
SLI	1	2	3	4	Total
Good	0	2	4	0	6
Moderate	5	7	10	7	29
Poor	4	3	10	8	25
Total	9	12	24	15	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	d f	p
χ^2	5.88	6	.437
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD7 (hours) category, $\chi^2 (6, N = 60) = 5.88$, $p = 0.437$. The distribution of SD7 categories did not differ significantly across SLI levels, with

comparable patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.”

Table: 6.8 Contingency Tables

	SD8				
SLI	1	2	3	4	Total
Good	1	3	1	1	6
Moderate	4	10	8	7	29
Poor	6	11	4	4	25
Total	11	24	13	12	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	2.63	6	.853
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD8 (hobbies) category, χ^2 (6, N = 60) = 2.63, $p = 0.853$. The distribution of SD8 categories did not differ significantly across SLI levels,

with similar patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.”

Table: 6.8 Contingency Tables

	SD8				
SLI	1	2	3	4	Total
Good	1	3	1	1	6
Moderate	4	10	8	7	29
Poor	6	11	4	4	25
Total	11	24	13	12	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	df	p
χ^2	2.63	6	.853
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD8 (hobbies) category, χ^2 (6, N = 60) = 2.63, $p = 0.853$. The distribution of SD8 categories

did not differ significantly across SLI levels, with similar patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.”

Table: 6.9 Contingency Tables

	SD9				
SLI	1	2	3	4	Total
Good	2	1	3	0	6
Moderate	4	15	8	2	29
Poor	8	13	4	0	25
Total	14	29	15	2	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	d f	p
χ^2	8.10	6	.231
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD9 (locality) category, χ^2 (6, N = 60) = 8.10, p = 0.231. The distribution of SD9 categories

did not differ significantly across SLI levels, with similar patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.”

Table: 6.10 Contingency Tables

	SD10			
SLI	1	2	3	Total
Good	0	1	5	6
Moderate	2	5	22	29
Poor	1	2	22	25
Total	3	8	49	60

χ^2 Tests			
	Value	d f	p
χ^2	1.72	4	.787
N	60		

Interpretation: “The analysis showed no significant association between SLI level and SD10 (socio-economic status) category, χ^2 (4, N = 60) = 1.72, p = 0.787. The distribution of ”

SD10 categories did not differ significantly across SLI levels, with similar patterns observed among good, moderate, and poor groups.

Chapter 5 Results

This chapter gives a detailed account of the results of present study.

The present study was intended to assess the web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students of UC IJMSRT26MAY022

College Aluva.

5.1 Objectives

1. To assess the level of web series addiction among college students.
2. To assess the sleeping pattern of college students.
3. To assess the relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in various college of Aluva.
4. To find the association between web series addiction and selected demographical variables of college students.
5. To find the association between sleeping pattern and selected demographical variables of college students.

5.2 Assumptions

1. Sleep is a basic human need essential for maintaining physical and mental health.
2. Web series watching is a common activity among college students.
3. Excessive watching of web series may affect normal sleeping patterns.
4. Sleep pattern can be influenced by behavioral and lifestyle factors.

5.3 Hypothesis

- There is a significant association between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students.

5.4 Result

The major findings of the study are summarized under following section

1. Description of level of web series addiction among college students
2. Description of sleeping pattern of college students
3. Inference of relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in various colleges at Aluva
4. Inference of association between web series addiction and selected demographic variables of college students
4. Inference of association between sleeping pattern and selected demographic variables of college students

5.4.1. Description of level of web series addiction among college students

The findings reveal that the majority of college students had moderate level of web series addiction (62%), followed by severe addiction (22%), while only 16% of students had mild addiction. This indicates that most students

are moderately addicted to web series, with a considerable proportion also experiencing severe addiction.

5.4.2. Description of sleeping pattern of college students

The findings show that nearly half of the students had moderate sleep hygiene (48.4%), followed by poor sleep hygiene (41.6%), while only 10% of students had good sleep hygiene. This indicates that most students have unsatisfactory sleeping patterns, with a considerable proportion experiencing poor sleep hygiene.

5.4.3. Inference of relationship between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students studying in various colleges at Aluva

The analysis showed a significant association between web series and sleeping pattern. The correlation indicates a weak positive relationship between web series addiction and sleep disturbances, suggesting that higher levels of web series are associated with increased sleeping pattern disturbances.

5.4.4. Inference of association between web series addiction and selected demographic variables of college students

- Majority of the subjects (44%) were belongs to age of 23-25 years , 25% were in the age of 17-19 years , 18% belongs to 20-22 years and the 13% were in 23 years and above .
- Most of subjects (61.6%) were females.
- All subjects belongs to arts and humanities departments.
- Majority of subjects (55%) were in first year, 23% were in third year, 12% were in second year and remaining 10% in post graduates.
- Most of the subjects (61%) were day scholars, 32% were living in hostel and the remaining 7% were paying guest.
- Majority of the subjects (72%) uses mobile as their device for watching web series, 12% were using laptop, 13% uses smart TV and the remaining 3% were using tablets.
- Majority of the subjects (40%) spent 2-4 hours watching web series per day, 27% spent more than 4 hours, 20% spent 1-2 hours and the remaining 13 % spent less than 1 hour.
- Majority of the subjects (40%) hobbies were watching web series and 20% were watching reels , watching films and others

- Majority of the subjects (47%) were lives in semi urban locality, 25% were lives in rural locality, 23% were lives in urban locality and 5% belongs to semi-rural locality.
- Majority of the subjects (58%) were in middle class, 37% were in upper middle class and the remaining 5% belongs to upper class.

5.4.5. Inference of association between sleeping pattern and selected demographic variables of college students

- Majority of the subjects (44%) were belongs to age of 23-25 years , 25% were in the age of 17-19 years , 18% belongs to 20-22 years and the 13% were in 23 years and above .
- Most of subjects (61.6%) were females.
- All subjects belongs to arts and humanities departments.
- Majority of subjects (55%) were in first year, 23% were in third year, 12% were in second year and remaining 10% in post graduates.
- Most of the subjects (61%) were day scholars, 32% were living in hostel and the remaining 7% were paying guest.
- Majority of the subjects (72%) uses mobile as their device for watching web series, 12% were using laptop, 13% uses smart TV and the remaining 3% were using tablets.
- Majority of the subjects (40%) spent 2-4 hours watching web series per day, 27% spent more than 4 hours , 20% spent 1-2 hours and the remaining 13 % spent less than 1 hour .
- Majority of the subjects (40%) hobbies were watching web series and 20% were watching reels , watching films and others
- Majority of the subjects (47%) were lives in semi urban locality, 25% were lives in rural locality , 23% were lives in urban locality and 5% belongs to semi-rural locality.
- Majority of the subjects (58%) were in middle class, 37% were in upper middle class and the remaining 5% belongs to upper class.

5.5.Summary

The results of the study showed that there is a significant association between web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students. The study also identified that higher levels of web series are associated with increased sleeping pattern disturbances

Chapter 6 Discussion,Summaryand Conclusion

This chapter gives a brief account of the present study including a discussion of findings, conclusions drawn ,limitations of the study , nursing implications and the recommendations for future research.

6.1 Discussion

The present study was conducted to assess the level of web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students in selected colleges at Aluva. The findings were also discussed in relation to observations made by other investigators.

In the present study, the majority of students (62%) had moderate web series addiction, followed by 22% with severe addiction and 16% with mild addiction. These findings are consistent with previous studies, where investigators have reported that a large proportion of college students engage in frequent binge-watching of web series and digital content. Similar studies have highlighted that the widespread use of smartphones, easy internet accessibility, and availability of OTT platforms have significantly increased screen dependency among young adults. Some researchers have also found that a notable percentage of students exhibit addictive viewing behavior, which aligns with the proportion of moderate to severe addiction observed in the present study.

Regarding sleeping patterns, the present study revealed that 48.4% of students had moderate sleep hygiene, 41.6% had poor sleep hygiene, and only 10% had good sleep hygiene. These findings are in agreement with other studies, which have reported that a majority of college students experience inadequate or disturbed sleep patterns. Previous investigators have identified factors such as late-night screen usage, academic stress, and irregular daily routines as major contributors to poor sleep hygiene among students.

Furthermore, the present study findings support earlier research that suggests a relationship between excessive screen time and poor sleep quality. Many studies have reported that prolonged exposure to screens, especially before bedtime, can lead to delayed sleep onset, reduced sleep duration, and impaired sleep quality. This is mainly due to the

effect of blue light on melatonin secretion and the stimulating nature of digital content. The current study's observation of a high proportion of students with moderate to poor sleep hygiene is consistent with these findings.

Additionally, other investigators have emphasized that behavioral factors and lifestyle habits play a significant role in influencing sleep patterns among college students. The present study also reflects similar trends, where increased engagement in web series watching may contribute to irregular sleep schedules and poor sleep practices.

However, slight variations in findings across studies may be due to differences in sample size, study setting, cultural background, and assessment tools used.

Overall, the present study findings are largely supported by existing literature, reinforcing the evidence that excessive web series consumption is common among college students and is associated with disturbed sleeping patterns.

6.2 Summary

The study was conducted to assess the level of web series addiction and sleeping pattern among college students in selected colleges at Aluva. The findings showed that most students had moderate web series addiction (62%), and a significant number had moderate (48.4%) to poor (41.6%) sleep hygiene. The study highlights a possible link between increased screen time and disturbed sleep patterns. It emphasizes the need for health education, preventive strategies, and further research to improve student well-being.

6.3 Conclusion

The study concludes that web series addiction is prevalent among college students, with most students showing moderate to severe levels. Additionally, the sleeping pattern of students is not satisfactory, with a majority having moderate to poor sleep hygiene. This highlights the need for awareness and interventions to promote healthy media usage and proper sleep habits among students.

6.4 Nursing implications

The present study has significant implications in the field of nursing administration, nursing education, nursing practice and nursing research

Nursing education

- Provide education on the importance of proper sleep and its impact on health.
- Include topics like web series addiction, screen time, and sleep hygiene in the curriculum.
- Conduct awareness programs and health talks for students on healthy lifestyle habits.
- Educate students about the negative effects of excessive screen usage, especially at night.

Nursing practice

- Assess students for sleep patterns and screen usage habits during health check-ups.
- Identify students with poor sleep hygiene and addictive behaviors.
- Provide individual counseling and guidance to improve sleep habits.
- Encourage practices like limiting screen time before bedtime and maintaining a sleep routine.

Nursing administration

- Organize health education campaigns and workshops in colleges.
- Develop and implement programs promoting digital well-being and healthy sleep.
- Facilitate collaboration between nurses, teachers, and parents to monitor student health.
- Ensure availability of counselling services for students with addiction-related issues.

Nursing Research

- Conduct further studies on web series addiction and its health effects.
- Explore intervention strategies to reduce screen addiction among students.
- Carry out comparative studies in different settings or populations.
- Promote research on long-term impact of poor sleep hygiene on student health.

6.5 Limitations

- The study was limited to selected colleges in Aluva, so generalization is limited.
- The sample size was relatively small.
- Data collection was based on self-reported responses, which may include bias.
- Other factors affecting sleep (stress, health issues) were not deeply explored.

6.6 Recommendations

- Conduct similar studies with a larger sample size and wider area.
- Implement intervention programs to reduce web series addiction.
- Encourage students to follow proper sleep hygiene practices.
- Include longitudinal studies to assess long-term effects.
- Create awareness campaigns on digital addiction and sleep health.

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